

Low-Grade Uterine Adenosarcoma in a Postmenopausal Patient: A Case Report and Literature Review

Natalia Camejo ,
Cecilia Castillo

Department of Clinical Oncology, School of Medicine, University
of Uruguay, Montevideo, Uruguay

Abstract

Low-grade uterine adenosarcoma is a rare neoplasm accounting for 5.5–9 % of all uterine sarcomas. First described by Clement and Scully in 1974, it is characterized by benign endometrial glands combined with a low-grade malignant mesenchymal stroma. We report the case of a 77-year-old woman without known risk factors (endometriosis, hormonal therapy, or pelvic radiotherapy) who presented with intermittent metrorrhagia. Pelvic ultrasound and clinical examination revealed a uterine mass, and diagnostic hysteroscopy with polypectomy confirmed low-grade adenosarcoma (5 mitoses per 10 high-power fields, moderate stromal invasion). Pelvic MRI demonstrated a well-circumscribed lesion measuring 54 × 68 × 100 mm without deep myometrial invasion or dissemination. The patient underwent total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy; the surgical specimen confirmed FIGO stage IB disease with positive estrogen and progesterone receptors. Following an uneventful postoperative course and a negative chest CT, adjuvant therapy with anastrozole 1 mg daily was initiated, and follow-up was scheduled every three months clinically and every six months with pelvic imaging.

This case underscores the importance of precise histopathological diagnosis, long-term surveillance, and the potential benefit of adjuvant hormone therapy in the absence of sarcomatous overgrowth.

Introduction

Uterine sarcomas account for only 1 % of malignant neoplasms of the female genital tract and 3–7 % of uterine body tumors, making them relatively uncommon oncologic entities [22]. Histologically, they may originate from the myometrial smooth muscle (leiomyosarcomas), the endometrial stroma (endometrial stromal sarcoma and undifferentiated endometrial sarcoma) [23], or a combination of both, resulting in adenosarcomas [1,2]. Since 2009, FIGO has proposed a staging system that groups uterine sarcomas into two categories—leiomyosarcoma and endometrial stromal sarcoma on one hand, and adenosarcoma on the other—distinguishing them from carcinosarcomas (mixed Müllerian tumors), which are now managed as endometrial carcinomas, and from endometrial adenocarcinomas [1,3,4].

Uterine adenosarcoma represents approximately 5.5–9 % of all uterine sarcomas and is most frequently

diagnosed in postmenopausal women, although cases in younger patients have also been reported [5,6]. First described by Clement and Scully in 1974, it is characterized by the coexistence of benign glands—which may exhibit focal atypia—and a low-grade malignant stromal component [5]. Clinically, patients commonly present with abnormal uterine bleeding, a polypoid mass protruding through the cervical canal, pelvic pain, or an abdominal mass [5,6]. In roughly 60 % of cases, the disease is confined to the uterus (stage I), and five-year overall survival is approximately 80 %. Poor prognostic factors include myometrial invasion, lymphovascular involvement, heterologous differentiation, and, most notably, sarcomatous overgrowth—defined as ≥ 25 % of the tumor volume—which increases recurrence rates to 70–80 % and reduces five-year survival to around 50 % [8]. Total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy is the treatment of choice [24], and

More Information

How to cite this article: Camejo N, Garcia M, Castillo C, Krygier G. Low-Grade Uterine Adenosarcoma in a Postmenopausal Patient: A Case Report and Literature Review. *Eur J Med Health Res*, 2025;3(3):138-41.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(3).21

Keywords:

Adenosarcoma,
Uterine Neoplasms,
Endometrial Neoplasms,
Anastrozole,
Case Reports,
Postmenopause

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

routine lymphadenectomy is generally omitted due to the low incidence of nodal metastases [5,6]. The benefit of adjuvant radiotherapy and chemotherapy remains controversial, whereas hormone therapy may be considered in selected cases, particularly in the absence of sarcomatous overgrowth [6,9].

Case Presentation

A 77-year-old woman with no history of endometriosis, prolonged estrogen exposure, tamoxifen or other hormonal modulators, nor prior pelvic radiotherapy, presented with intermittent metrorrhagia. She denied abdominal or pelvic pain. Gynecological examination revealed a uterine mass without other notable findings. Diagnostic hysteroscopy with polypectomy and curettage was performed. Histopathology showed a biphasic proliferation consistent with low-grade adenosarcoma: benign epithelial glands and fronds lined by a single layer of non-atypical cells without mitoses, alongside a malignant mesenchymal stroma characterized by increased cellularity, spindle-shaped cells, moderate pleomorphism, 5 mitoses per 10 high-power fields, and a rich capillary network.

Staging pelvic MRI demonstrated a well-circumscribed endometrial lesion measuring 54 × 68 × 100 mm with intermediate T2 signal and focal diffusion restriction on ADC, without myometrial invasion. The mass extended to the internal cervical os but did not reach the external os, and there was no nodal or distant spread.

The patient underwent a total abdominal hysterectomy with a bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy via a laparotomy. Pathologic examination confirmed low-grade adenosarcoma with myometrial invasion of less than half the uterine wall and focal extension to the uterine isthmus, sparing the endocervix. Both uterine horns, parametrium, and cervix were free of tumor, with only nonspecific chronic cervicitis noted. The disease was staged as FIGO IB. Immunohistochemistry was positive for estrogen and progesterone receptors. Postoperative recovery was uneventful. A chest CT scan showed no evidence of metastasis. Given the FIGO IB stage and absence of additional risk factors, the patient was started on adjuvant anastrozole 1 mg daily. Follow-up was scheduled with clinical evaluations every three months and pelvic imaging every six months.

Discussion

Müllerian adenosarcomas of the female genital tract are rare malignant neoplasms first described by Clement and Scully in 1974 [5]. They most commonly occur between 40 and 65 years of age, although cases in both younger and older patients have been reported [10]. Known risk factors include tamoxifen or toremifene therapy, endometriosis, and pelvic radiotherapy [6,10-12]; our patient had none of these, underscoring the importance of considering adenosarcoma even in the absence of classic predisposing factors.

Clinically, abnormal uterine bleeding is the hallmark symptom, often accompanied by a rapidly growing pelvic mass. Physical examination may reveal a polypoid lesion protruding through the cervical canal or a palpable mass in more advanced cases [1,12,13]; in our report, preoperative assessment was limited by the lack of a detailed exam record. Transvaginal ultrasound—useful for identifying endometrial polyps, myometrial thickening, or features suggestive of malignancy—was unavailable for review (6). Measurement of serum CA-125, while not specific for adenosarcoma, can aid in postoperative monitoring and early detection of recurrence [1,6,13,14].

Definitive diagnosis requires histopathology, identifying a low-grade malignant stromal component alongside benign glands. It is critical to distinguish adenosarcoma from adenofibroma—which lacks atypia and shows low mitotic activity—and from carcinosarcoma, which carries a poorer prognosis due to both epithelial and stromal malignancy. Endometrial stromal sarcoma can “trap” glands and mimic adenosarcoma, often necessitating immunohistochemistry (e.g., CD10, WT1) to confirm Müllerian origin [9,15-17]. In our case, estrogen and progesterone receptor positivity was confirmed, although p53—whose overexpression correlates with more aggressive behavior—was not assessed [6,9].

Surgical staging following the FIGO system is essential for prognosis and guiding adjuvant therapy. The absence of deep myometrial invasion and nodal involvement in stage IB generally obviates routine lymphadenectomy, given the low risk of nodal metastases [1,4,8]. A chest CT ruled out distant spread. Radical surgery—total abdominal hysterectomy with bilateral salpingo-oophorectomy—is the treatment of choice in early stages, particularly to address potential adnexal extension [1,5,6]. In the absence of sarcomatous overgrowth, adjuvant hormone therapy gains relevance: responses have been documented with GnRH agonists, progestins, aromatase inhibitors, and selective estrogen receptor modulators, with durations ranging from 10 months to 7 years [13,18]. In our patient, anastrozole was well tolerated. Adjuvant radiotherapy and chemotherapy lack robust support from controlled trials; however, some studies suggest palliative benefit of radiation in high-risk tumors [8,19,20] and isolated responses to doxorubicin/ifosfamide or gemcitabine/docetaxel regimens in high-grade sarcomas [1-3,5].

Follow-up should be tailored to prognostic factors—myometrial invasion, sarcomatous overgrowth, and heterologous differentiation. In patients without adverse features, recurrence risk is low, and clinical evaluation every three months with imaging every six months is typically sufficient [13,21]. The absence of a universally accepted surveillance protocol highlights

the value of multidisciplinary discussion—ideally in a tumor board—to optimize both initial management and long-term follow-up.

Conclusions

Uterine adenosarcoma is a rare neoplasm that, when diagnosed at an early stage and without sarcomatous overgrowth, is generally associated with a favorable prognosis. However, the presence of a significant sarcomatous component and myometrial invasion markedly increases the risk of recurrence and mortality, justifying the consideration of adjuvant therapies in these cases. Given the propensity for late relapses, it is essential to establish a long-term follow-up program combining clinical evaluations and imaging studies. Finally, prospective research is needed to optimize therapeutic and surveillance strategies with the goal of improving both survival and quality of life for these patients.

Informed Consent Statement

Written informed consent has been obtained from the patient to publish this case report.

Acknowledgments

None.

Conflict of Interests

Authors declare no conflict of interest.

Funding

The author(s) received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article

Availability of Data

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author through email upon reasonable request.

References

[1] Li JY, Mutlu L, Tymon-Rosario J, et al. Clinicopathologic characteristics and oncologic outcomes in adenosarcoma of gynecologic sites. *Gynecol Oncol Rep*. 2021 Dec 20;39:100913. doi: 10.1016/j.gore.2021.100913.

[2] Prat J, Mbatani '. Uterine sarcomas. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2015 Oct;131 Suppl 2:S105-10. doi: 10.1016/j.ijgo.2015.06.006. P

[3] Chern JY, Boyd LR, Blank SV. Uterine Sarcomas: The Latest Approaches for These Rare but Potentially Deadly Tumors. *Oncology (Williston Park)*. 2017 Mar 15;31(3):229-36..

[4] Prat J. FIGO staging for uterine sarcomas. *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2009 Mar;104(3):177-8. doi: 10.1016/j.ijgo.2008.12.008. Epub 2009 Jan 9. Erratum in: *Int J Gynaecol Obstet*. 2009 Sep;106(3):277.

[5] Nathenson MJ, Ravi V, Fleming N, Wang WL, Conley A. Uterine Adenosarcoma: a Review. *Curr Oncol Rep*. 2016 Nov;18(11):68. doi: 10.1007/s11912-016-0552-7.

[6] Ulrich UA, Denschlag D. Uterine Adenosarcoma. *Oncol Res Treat*. 2018;41(11):693-696. doi: 10.1159/000494067.

[7] Han XY, Xiang Y, Guo LN, et al. [Mullerian adenosarcoma of the uterus: A clinicopathologic analysis of 9 cases]. *Zhonghua Zhong Liu Za Zhi*. 2010 Jan;32(1):44-7. Chinese.

[8] Arend R, Bagaria M, Lewin SN, et al. Long-term outcome and natural history of uterine adenosarcomas. *Gynecol Oncol*. 2010 Nov;119(2):305-8. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2010.07.001.

[9] D'Angelo E, Prat J. Uterine sarcomas: a review. *Gynecol Oncol*. 2010 Jan;116(1):131-9. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2009.09.023. Epub 2009 Oct 23.

[10] Friedlander ML, Covens A, Glasspool RM, et al. Gynecologic Cancer InterGroup (GCIg) consensus review for mullerian adenosarcoma of the female genital tract. *Int J Gynecol Cancer*. 2014 Nov;24(9 Suppl 3):S78-82. doi: 10.1097/IGC.0000000000000239.

[11] Chung YW, Bae HS, Han SI, Song JY, Kim IS, Kang JS. Endometrial mullerian adenosarcoma after toremifene treatment in breast cancer patients: a case report. *J Gynecol Oncol*. 2010 Dec 30;21(4):269-72. doi: 10.3802/jgo.2010.21.4.269.

[12] Clement PB, Scully RE. Mullerian adenosarcoma of the uterus: a clinicopathologic analysis of 100 cases with a review of the literature. *Hum Pathol*. 1990 Apr;21(4):363-81. doi: 10.1016/0046-8177(90)90198-e.

[13] Carroll A, Ramirez PT, Westin SN, et al. Uterine adenosarcoma: an analysis on management, outcomes, and risk factors for recurrence. *Gynecol Oncol*. 2014 Dec;135(3):455-61. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2014.10.022.

[14] Kaku T, Silverberg SG, Major FJ, Miller A, Fetter B, Brady MF. Adenosarcoma of the uterus: a Gynecologic Oncology Group clinicopathologic study of 31 cases. *Int J Gynecol Pathol*. 1992;11(2):75-88.

[15] McCluggage WG. Mullerian adenosarcoma of the female genital tract. *Adv Anat Pathol*. 2010 Mar;17(2):122-9. doi: 10.1097/PAP.0b013e3181cfe732.

[16] Shah SH, Jagannathan JP, Krajewski K, O'Regan KN, George S, Ramaiya NH. Uterine sarcomas: then and now. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2012 Jul;199(1):213-23. doi: 10.2214/AJR.11.7287.

[17] Soslow RA, Ali A, Oliva E. Mullerian adenosarcomas: an immunophenotypic analysis of 35 cases. *Am J Surg Pathol*. 2008 Jul;32(7):1013-21. doi: 10.1097/PAS.0b013e318161d1be.

[18] Wang Q, Sun S, Cai J, Yang L, Lv G, Yang Q. Uterine adenosarcoma: a case report and review of the literature. *Am J Nucl Med Mol Imaging*. 2023 Apr 25;13(2):70-76.

[19] Tanner EJ, Toussaint T, Leitao MM Jr, et al. Management of uterine adenosarcomas with and without sarcomatous overgrowth. *Gynecol Oncol*. 2013 Apr;129(1):140-4. doi: 10.1016/j.ygyno.2012.12.036. Epub 2012 Dec 30.

- [20] Sampath S, Gaffney DK. Role of radiotherapy treatment of uterine sarcoma. *Best Pract Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol.* 2011 Dec;25(6):761-72. doi: 10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2011.06.004. Epub 2011 Jul 23.
- [21] Nathenson MJ, Conley AP, Lin H, Fleming N, Ravi V. Treatment of Recurrent or Metastatic Uterine Adenosarcoma. *Sarcoma.* 2017;2017:4680273. doi: 10.1155/2017/4680273. Epub 2017 Dec 28.
- [22] Moinfar F, Azodi M, Tavassoli FA. Uterine sarcomas. *Pathology.* 2007 Feb;39(1):55–71.

- [23] Sud S, Gupta S, Buxi TBS, Ghuman SS, Sethi S, Jain S, Gupta M, Sud A, Rastogi D. MR Imaging Spectrum of Uterine and Cervical Lesions – Expanding the Differential Diagnosis. *ECR 2015; Poster No.: C-1131.*
- [24] Zagouri F, Linardou H, Dimopoulos AM, Papadimitriou CA. Management of advanced stage uterine sarcomas: A bone of contention. *Eur J Gynaecol Oncol.* 2009;30(5):483–492.

